

Kinetic studies on the reactions of *O*-(2',4'-dinitrophenyl) 1,7,7-trimethylbicyclo[2.2.1]heptan-2-one oxime with nucleophiles in aprotic solvents – mechanism for the uncatalysed pathway

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Abstract : Kinetics of the reactions of the title compound with some amines as nucleophiles in aprotic solvents have been investigated at the λ_{\max} of the aminolysis product at 35 ± 0.1 °C under pseudo-first order conditions. The reaction is overall second order, first with respect to each reactant. The second order rate coefficients decreased with increase in [amine] in all cases. Formation of an electron donor-acceptor complex is indicated. The temperature effect on the reaction rate has been studied in the range (293–318 K). The entropy of activation parameters are large and negative in all cases indicating formation of a crowded transition state. Mechanistic interpretation is given.

Keywords : Aprotic solvents, amines, electron donor-acceptor complex.

Nucleophilic aromatic substitution reactions of nitro or halogen activated substrates with novel nucleophiles in protic and aprotic solvents are of active research interest¹ because of synthetic utility² in medicinal³ and polymer chemistry⁴. A number of investigations with primary and secondary amines as nucleophiles are reported^{5,6}. In some cases it has been shown that base catalysis occurs with nucleophiles of high basicity⁷. In some cases, however it has been found that the catalytic effect does not depend on the basicity of the amine⁸. Emokpae coworkers⁹ studied mechanism of ANS reactions with bulky nucleofuges. However, substrates with sterically bulky nucleofuges have not been studied in detail and still is a subject of discussion¹⁰. The reactions of the title compound with cyclohexylamine (CHA) and piperidine (PIP) were carried out⁶ in aqueous acetonitrile and found to be base catalysed only with PIP. Solvents play a strategic role in reactions of this type. Katangiri and coworkers¹¹ reported complete retention of stereochemical integrity at the P-

stereogenic center during S_NAr process when the reaction was carried out in THF at low temperature and helped in the synthesis of optically pure P-chiral (dialkyl)arylphosphine-boranes. Proper choice of solvent is important.

Table 1. Effect of nucleophile on the rate of the reactions of **2** in acetonitrile at 35 ± 0.1 °C

Nucleophile	[Substrate] = 8.0×10^{-5} mol dm ⁻³		
	[Nu]/10 ⁻² (mol dm ⁻³)	$k_o/10^{-4}$ (s ⁻¹)	$k_f/10^{-4}$ (mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹ dm ³)
Piperidine	0.09	4.43	4922.0
	0.10	4.85	4850.0
	0.30	13.98	4660.0
	0.50	21.87	4374.0
	0.65	27.77	4272.0
Cyclohexylamine	10.0	0.48	4.8
	20.0	0.89	4.5
	30.0	1.26	4.2
	40.0	1.56	3.9
	50.0	2.01	4.0
Ethanolamine	5.0	0.66	13.2
	10.0	1.13	11.3
	20.0	2.02	10.1
	30.0	2.54	8.5
	40.0	3.64	9.1
Pyrrolidine	50.0	4.33	8.7
	1.0	0.28	28.0
	2.0	0.51	25.5
	3.0	0.69	23.0
	4.0	0.89	22.3
5.0	1.10	22	

We studied aminolysis reactions of the title compound **2** in aprotic solvents, the results of which are reported and discussed in this paper.

Results and discussion

The plots of the first order rate constants, k_o versus [amine] were straight lines passing through the origin in all cases. The plots of the second order rate constants, $k_r = k_o/[amine]$ versus [amine] for the reactions of compound **2** with piperidine, cyclohexylamine, ethanolamine and pyrrolidine in acetonitrile were curvilinear and concave towards the rate axis in each case. The results are summarized in Table 1. Similar observations were reported by some earlier workers¹².

In the present case it seems that the intermediate complex (T^\ddagger) in Scheme 1 gets more and more stabilized through complex formation/hydrogen bond formation with the nucleophile and the second order rate constants decrease with increase in [amine]. A comparison of pK_a values of some amines (Table 2) reveals that base strength increases by a large extent in acetonitrile and consequently the ammonium proton in T^\ddagger (Scheme 1) does not dissociate easily and results in charge accumulation on the amine nitrogen. This facilitates formation of a complex with amine at high amine concentration involving the ammonium proton. The order of nucleophilic reactivity towards compound **2** in acetonitrile is as follows: piperidine > pyrrolidine > ethanolamine > cyclohexylamine.

Table 2. The pK_a values of amines in water and acetonitrile (25)

Nucleophile	pK_a in water	pK_a in MeCN
Piperidine	11.22	18.92
Pyrrolidine	11.12	18.60 ^a
Cyclohexylamine	10.64	18.30 ^a
Ethanolamine	9.44	16.70 ^a
<i>n</i> -Butylamine	10.59	18.26
Benzylamine	9.37	16.76
Morpholine	8.31	16.60
4-Methylpyridine	6.08	13.65

^a = estimated value

It is evident that piperidine is the most reactive nucleophile in this reaction. The pK_a value of piperidine in acetonitrile is available but the corresponding values for others in this medium were not available. Hence, a rough estimation of pK_a values of cyclohexylamine, pyrrolidine and ethanolamine were made from a plot of pK_a in water vs pK_a acetonitrile. It is true that in the present case ΔH^\ddagger value for pyrrolidine is the least of all the nucleophilies used. but the reactivity of piperidine is the highest. On conformational considerations, the six-membered piperidine ring is more strain free than the five-membered pyrrolidine. Further, the reaction with pyrrolidine has the highest negative ΔS^\ddagger value and that with piperidine has the lowest ΔG^\ddagger value. Except ethanolamine, the reactivity

Scheme 1

of other nucleophiles are in order of their pK_a values. The high reactivity of ethanolamine compared to cyclohexylamine is attributed to the presence of hydroxyl group which exerts its electron withdrawing inductive effect and helps in the decomposition of the intermediate complex. Transfer of proton from N to O as shown in Scheme 2 helps in the detachment of the leaving group and form the product.

Table 3. Effect of solvent polarity on the rate of the reaction of **2** with piperidine at 35 ± 0.1 °C

[Substrate] = 8.0×10^{-5} mol dm ⁻³				
Solvent	[Nu]/10 ⁻³ (mol dm ⁻³)	$k_o/10^{-4}$ (s ⁻¹)	$k_r/10^{-2}$ (mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹ dm ³)	
Acetonitrile	0.9	4.43	49.2	
	1.0	4.85	48.5	
	3.0	13.98	46.6	
	5.0	21.87	43.7	
	6.5	27.77	42.7	
	Ethylacetate	1.0	1.56	15.6
		2.3	3.56	15.5
3.5		5.46	15.6	
5.5		8.38	15.2	
7.5		11.53	15.4	
Toluene	0.9	0.78	8.70	
	1.0	0.90	9.00	
	3.0	2.52	8.40	
	4.5	3.93	8.70	
	6.5	5.60	8.60	
Tetrahydrofuran	0.7	2.21	31.6	
	1.0	3.15	31.5	
	2.9	9.06	31.2	
	3.9	12.20	31.5	
	4.5	14.32	31.8	

Scheme 2

Taking stereochemistry into consideration, the attack of the nucleophile from the *endo* site is feasible as the *exo* site is sterically blocked by the methyl groups at positions C-1 and C-7.

group is the active nucleophile, the expected product would be *O*-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)ethanolamine. The product isolated was found to be identical with *N*-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)ethanolamine procured from Sigma. This confirmed that the amino nitrogen of ethanolamine was the active nucleophile in the reactions studied.

Table 4. Effect of temperature on the rate of reactions of 2 with different nucleophiles in acetonitrile

Nucleophile	[Nu]/10 ⁻² (mol dm ⁻³)	Temp (K)	k _v /10 ⁻⁴ (s ⁻¹)
Piperidine	0.07	303	2.60
		308	3.28
		313	3.66
		318	4.14
		313	4.51
Cyclohexylamine	40.0	293	0.87
		298	1.06
		303	1.35
		308	1.57
		313	2.10
Ethanolamine	40.0	298	2.74
		303	2.84
		308	3.64
		313	4.51
		313	4.51
Pyrrolidine	4.0	293	0.87
		298	0.92
		303	0.96
		308	1.01
		313	1.07

In ethanolamine two nucleophilic sites are available (ambident nucleophile) for nucleophilic attack at the aromatic carbon. If amino nitrogen is the active site, then the expected product would be *N*-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)ethanolamine. On the other hand if the lone pair on the oxygen of the hydroxyl

Table 5. Activation parameters for the reactions of 2 with different nucleophiles

Nucleophile	ΔG [‡] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-ΔS [‡] (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔH [‡] (kJ mol ⁻¹)
Piperidine	78.5 (±1.85)	182.59 (±0.44)	21.33 (±0.081)
Cyclohexylamine	96.5 (±2.16)	200.20 (±0.94)	33.80 (±0.12)
Ethanolamine	96.5 (±2.18)	197.90 (±1.36)	32.50 (±0.084)
Pyrrolidine	92.3 (±4.24)	277.90 (±0.68)	5.30 (±0.13)

It seems that in acetonitrile the decomposition of the intermediate complex (T[‡]) is hampered due to low acidity of the protons attached to ammonium nitrogen and localization of charge on the latter occurs. At higher base concentration, the intermediate complex (T[‡]) gets stabilized by complex formation involving ammonium proton and amine giving rise to curvilinear response.

The effect of solvent on the reaction of compound 2 with piperidine was studied in acetonitrile, ethyl acetate, tetrahydrofuran and toluene. In each case the products were *N*-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)piperidine and the parent oxime 1. The reaction was affected when the solvent was changed from non polar to dipolar aprotic¹³ or from protic to aprotic¹⁴.

From Table 1 it is evident that the second order rate coefficients, k_t decreased slightly with increase in [amine] in all cases indicating non-catalysed reactions¹⁵. The reactions of **2** were also carried out in different acetonitrile-water media⁶ with piperidine and cyclohexylamine. Base catalysis was observed in the case of piperidine only. In this case the decomposition of the intermediate complex was facilitated in weakly polar medium and the rate of the reaction increased with increase in the percentage of acetonitrile in the medium.

Table 6. Physical constants and spectral data of compounds **1** and **2**

Compd.	Colour	m.p. (°C) obs./ lit.	Spectral data
1,7,7-Trimethyl- [2.2.1]heptan-2-one oxime (1)	Colourless	116/117	IR 3300 (νO-H, bonded), 1660 (νC=N) cm ⁻¹ ; ¹ H NMR (90 MHz) δ 0.80 (3H, s, β-Me), 0.93 (3H, s, α-Me), 1.02 (3H, s, γ-Me), 1.16–2.3 (6H, m, -CH ₂ -), 2.62 (1H, m, -CH-), 9.23 (1H, bs, O-H)
O-(2',4'-Dinitrophenyl) 1,7,7-trimethyl-bicyclo- [2.2.1]heptan-2-one oxime (2)	Pale yellow	62/-	IR 1606 (νC=N), 1537, 1346 (νNO ₂), 930 (νN-O) cm ⁻¹ ; ¹ H NMR (90 MHz) δ 0.80 (3H, s, β-Me), 0.93 (3H, s, α-Me), 1.02 (3H, s, γ-Me), 1.14–2.22 (6H, m, -CH ₂ -), 2.59 (1H, m, -CH-), 7.3–8.95 (3H, m, aromatic); UV λ _{max} (acetonitrile) 282 nm (log ε = 4.09)

Temperature dependence :

Thermodynamic parameters provide sufficient information about the nature of the transition state of the reaction¹⁶. Keeping this in mind the reactions of **2** were studied with each of the four nucleophiles at different temperatures ranging from 293–318 K in acetonitrile. All the reactions followed Arrhenius relationship. Plots of log k_t versus $1/T$ were linear, and various activation parameters were calculated¹⁷ using appropriate relationships and are given in Table 5. The entropy of activation was negative in each case indicating a considerable decrease in randomness in the activated complex¹⁸. High negative values of ΔS^\ddagger further point to the development of charge and also the crowded nature of the transition state in each case.

Experimental

Solvents used were purified by literature method¹⁹. The nucleophiles were used after distillation and verification of their boiling points. All the solvents used were kept over 4 Å

molecular sieves. 1,7,7-Trimethylbicyclo[2.2.1]heptan-2-one (B.D.H.) was purified by sublimation (m.p. 179 °C). Compound **2** was prepared in two steps, first to oxime **1** by standard procedure²⁰ and then conversion of **1** to the dinitrophenyl derivative **2**. Oxime **1** (1.7 g, 0.01 mol) was dissolved in methanol and treated with a methanolic solution of 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene (2 g, 0.01 mol) and sodium methoxide (0.54 g, 0.01 mol). The reaction mixture was stirred, warmed and cooled to obtain **2**. It was recrystallised from absolute ethanol. The relevant physical constants and spectral data of **1** and **2** are given in Table 6.

Table 7. Physical constants of the products

Name of the product	m.p. (°C)	R_f values ^a Product (authentic sample)	λ _{max} (log ε) solvent (nm)
<i>N</i> -(2,4-Dinitrophenyl)- cyclohexylamine	119	0.91(0.92)	354 (4.20) CH ₃ CN
<i>N</i> -(2,4-Dinitrophenyl)- piperidine	79	0.94 (0.94)	382.5 (4.06) CH ₃ CN
<i>N</i> -(2,4-Dinitrophenyl)- piperidine	66	0.94 (0.94)	371.5 (4.23) THF
<i>N</i> -(2,4-Dinitrophenyl)- ethanolamine	92	0.94 (0.93)	351 (4.11) CH ₃ CN

^aSolvent system – C₆H₆ : CHCl₃ (1 : 1), silica gel (G).

The kinetics of the reactions of **2** with piperidine, cyclohexylamine, ethanolamine and pyrrolidine were carried out in acetonitrile as a function of amine concentration at the λ_{max} of the coloured aminolysis product (Table 7) at 35 ± 0.1 °C under pseudo first order conditions and followed the rate expression $\log(A_\infty - A_0)/(A_\infty - A_t) = k_0 t$, where A_∞ , A_t and A_0 are the absorbances at infinity, at time t and zero respectively. The reactions with piperidine have also been carried out in ethyl acetate, toluene and tetrahydrofuran. Shimadzu UV-2100 spectrophotometer equipped with 1.0 cm quartz cell was used for all spectral measurements. The stock solutions of the substrate and the nucleophile were used within 24 h. The solution of amine was placed in a quartz cuvette in a thermostatted cell compartment. The substrate solution having concentration (8.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³) was then injected into it and the absorbances were recorded at various timed intervals and A_∞ was recorded after 10 half-lives. The effect of temperature on the above reaction was studied in the range (293–318 K) with each of the four nucleophiles and the various activation parameters were evaluated. The reported rate data represent an average of duplicate runs reproducible to within ±4%. Kinetic runs having correlation coefficients less than 0.993 were discarded.

Product analysis :

The products of the reaction, *N*-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)amine and the parent oxime were obtained in quantitative yields. These products were characterized by direct comparison of

electronic spectra, R_f values and m.p. of the corresponding authentic samples. Some of the relevant physical constants and spectral data of the products are given in Table 7.

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